

Impact of Mental Toughness and Self Confidence Among Volleyball Players

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Abstract:- The major objectives of the study has been made to examine the role of physical factors like strength, speed, endurance, agility and flexibility on the mental toughness and self confidence of the volleyball players. It offers great movements in the body which are specifically measured on moter test like speed, endurance, strength, agility and flexibility by following available standred norms in the field of sports. A large sample was selected randomly on the whole physical factors and mental toughness and self confidence among factors. They were administered with test of resting heart rate, peak heat rate aerobic capacity, mental toughness and hemoglobin. After seoring the required sample (200) as per sample designe was selected thus and equal number of players were selected on the factor on whom the moter tests were conducted as per norms, the scores were subjected to statistical analysis.

I. INTRODUCTION

Mental toughness is a collection of attributes that allow a person to persevere through difficult circumstances (such as difficult training or difficult competitive situations in games) and emerge without losing confidence. In recent decades, the term ahs been commonly used by coaches, sport psychologist, sport commentators, and business leaders.

Self confidence is essential an attitude which allows us to have a positive and realistic perception of ourselves and our abilities. It is characterized by personal attributes such as assertiveness, optimism, enthusiasm, affection, pride, independence, trust, the ability to handle criticism and emotional maturity.

II. METHODOLOGY

➤ *Statement of the problem:*

The purpose of the study mental toughness and self confidence among volleyball players and non-volleyball players. The 200 samples from different colleges of jammu University.

➤ *Delimitations :*

- The study will be delimited to jammu university volleyball player.
- The study will be further delimited to age ranging 24 years.
- The study will be further confined to psychological variables.

➤ *Limitations*

- No motivational technique will be adopted to motivate the subjects.
- Special motivation techniques and verbal encouragement is provided throughout study.

➤ *Objectives*

- To find out the impact of mental toughness among volleyball player and non volleyball players.
- To find self confidence of the volleyball player and non volleyball players.

➤ *Hypothesis*

It is rather difficult to hypothesize since this study is related to volleyball and non volleyball players in relation to mental toughness and self confidence.

III. RESULTS

Table – 1 Mental Toughness of Volleyball players and Non-Volleyball Players

	M	SD	t-value
Volleyball Players	127.20	15.55	6.54**
Non Volleyball Players	145.10	11.00	

The mean score of volleyball players is higher than the non volleyball players. It shows that the volleyball players have high mental toughness and non volleyball players have low mental toughness. Because volleyball players involves in sports and physical activity that may represent resources, that do not only contribute to an increased well being, but also to an improved self confidence as a congntive representation of volleyball players mental toughness status. When t-value is 6.54, so it indicates the significant difference between these two groups, statistically significant at 0.05 level.

Table 2 Mental Toughness Level of Volley and Non-Volleyball Players on age factor

Sources	Age	Mean	SD	t-value
Volleyball Players	<24	130.20	16.70	1.61*
	>24	125.44	18.43	
Non volleyball Players	<24	145.23	10.55	0.53
	>24	144.12	9.88	

The mean score of below 24 age volleyball players is higher than the above 24 age volleyball players. It shows that the above 24 age. Volleyball players the better mental toughness than the below 24 age volleyball players. Because the above 24 age volleyball players are have more experiences, mentally matured in the game and also well settled in their life. When t-value was applied to know the significant difference it was found that obtained t-value is 1.61, so it indicates the significant difference between these two age groups of volleyball players. Statistically significant at 0.05 level.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

- The volleyball players have high impact of mental toughness and non volleyball players have low mental toughness.
- The above 24 age volleyball players have better impact of mental toughness than the below 24 age non volleyball players.

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